

Women in Tourism Industry

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Introduction

The term ‘Tourist’ is defined by World Tourism Organization as people who “travel to and stay in places outside their usual environment for more than twenty four hours and not more than one successive year for relaxation, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited”.

Another definition by the Tourism Society of England, it defines tourism as, “Tourism is the temporary, short term movement of people to destination outside the places where they normally live and work and their activities during the stay at each destination. It includes movements for all purposes”.

Tourism is fundamentally a manifestation of natural human character for experience, education and entertainment. The tourism sector is one among the sectors which are the fastest-growing sectors of the global economy, which accounts for 11 percent of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and employ around 225 million people worldwide.

Fundamentally, the tourism industry appears to be a significant sector for women (46% of the workforce are women) as their percentage of employment in most countries are higher than in the workforce in general. The numbers of women and their percentage of their workforce in tourism vary greatly between countries from 2% to up to over 80%. However, there were few obvious regional trends it would appear that in those countries where tourism is a more developed industry, women generally account for around 50% of the workforce.

The share of women’s to men’s working hours available, for 39 countries is 89%, which means that women work for 89 hours when men work for 100 hours. The ratio of women’s to men’s wages is 79%. Earning women are working for fewer hours than men and receive even less pay. However, it cannot be sure if this is due to women’s typical occupations being paid less, women being significantly more in part-time and/or temporary employment, and/or women being paid less for the same work.

Women Empowerment

Different people use empowerment to mean different things. But, there are four aspects which appear to be commonly recognised in the literature on women's empowerment. Originally to be empowered one must have been disempowered. It is pertinent to speak of empowering women, for example, because, as a group, they are disempowered relative to men. Furthermore, empowerment cannot be given by a third party. Somewhat those who would become empowered must claim it. Development agencies cannot, therefore, empower women so they can achieve is to facilitate women empowering themselves.

Women may be able to make conditions favourable to empowerment but they cannot make it happen. Thirdly, definitions of empowerment usually include a sense of people making decisions on matters which are important in their lives and being able to carry them out. Likeness, analysis and action are involved in this process which may happen on an individual or a collective level. There is some suggestion that while women's fights for empowerment have tended to be collective efforts, empowerment orientated development interventions often focus more on the level of the individual. Lastly, empowerment is an on-going process rather than a product. There is no final goal. One does not arrive at a stage of being empowered in some absolute sense. People are empowered, or disempowered, relative to others or, importantly, relative to themselves at a previous time.

Women in the Tourism Industry

Women are more likely to work in clerical services in tourism industries than compete with men at higher and more professional levels in tourism. Because of this, they are becoming victims of low paying jobs, unable to run homes efficiently. One can see this in one of the report findings by the World Tourism Organisation submitted and published in the year 2010. The social fear of giving women higher job positions has indirectly found them in a state of backwardness. The idea of a social fear preventing women from stepping out of their homes in today's culture might seem absurd. But in countries that are backward and undeveloped, it presents a safer option.

According to the WTTC 2013 Economic Impact Report, Travel and Tourism directly supported over 101 million jobs, representing 3.4% of total employment. Including jobs indirectly supported by the industry, Travel and Tourism supports 1 out of 11 jobs in the world, in the industry forecast by 2023.

Travel and Tourism provide unique work opportunities for females. In 2010 the World Tourism Organisation (UNWTO) and UN Women published a Global Report on Women in Tourism. This developed a series of indicators to monitor the role of women in tourism in developing regions. Closer to that of men than in other sectors and that Travel and Tourism provides opportunities for women as employers and self-employed work.

Horizontally, women are being employed as waitresses, chambermaids, cleaners, travel agencies salespersons, flight attendants and the like. Vertically, the typical gender pyramid is prevalent in the tourism sector – lower levels and occupation with few career development opportunities being dominated by women and key managerial positions being dominated by men. In the service sector, examining the occupations being particularly relevant in the tourism sector, it can be witnessed that more than 90% of women are working in catering & lodging, as waitresses, bartenders, maids, baby sitters, cleaners, housekeeping helpers, launderers, dry – cleaners and the like.

However, women have accomplished higher levels of education than ever before, their share in management position remains inadmissibly low, with a little proportion ensuing in breaking through the "glass ceiling". Around are some interlinked factors, that help to maintain gender, segregation of the labour market. Among them is gender stereotyping, traditional gender roles and gender identity – women are seen as being suitable for certain occupations and they seem

themselves as suitable. In addition to this the traditional gender roles assigned to women – the main responsibility of bearing and rearing children, caring for the elderly, and doing household work. Thus women are frequently forced to choose casual labour, part-time and seasonal employment.

Tourism sector benefits women to create self-employment. Community-based tourism initiatives, particular of local women's groups and co-operatives can be an accessible and suitable entry point for women to enter into the paid workforce. Many cases are there where women and women's groups have started income-generating activities on their own. These events help to create financial independence for local women and challenge them to develop the necessary skills and improve their education. The key constraint for the expansion of community-based tourism is marketing. Independent initiatives need more information about the market and potential customers. Tourists need to be provided with more information about the benefits of buying and using local goods and services. Access to information is provided at best by involving all stakeholders in planning and decision – making. Moreover, gender-specific information about tourists' needs and interests also help to serve customers, particularly women.

There are some statistics which show the extent of discrimination in hiring women as part of the workforce in the tourism industry:

1. Compared to youth, women have a lower rate of employment opportunities. About 39% of the workforce in tourism are occupied by the youth, giving little space for women ;
2. Other countries like the Bahamas have only 40% of seats reserved for women, whereas the other 60% is given to men. This 40% of jobs are relative to the hotel service sector in tourism than outdoor jobs which pay more;
3. Australia has a comparatively higher number i.e., 55.8% share for women. There are higher chances of women in Australia being promoted here than any other country;
4. India shows a meagre yet significant 38% of hiring vacancy for women. Some jobs though the same for both women and men still pay women less.
5. A lot of women working in family tourism businesses are unpaid
6. A vast difference in pay is seen where women earn 15% less salary than men in the tourism industry.

Tourism Sector in India

For the last two years, Tourism in India emerged as one of the major growth sectors of the Indian Economy. For earnings from tourism rose from Rs. 16,429 crore in 2004 to Rs.21,828 crores in 2005. Simultaneously there has been a 17.3 percent surge in foreign tourist arrivals, the highest over the last decade for the same period. The Ministry's capacity building funds have also increased with the Central tourism budget being upped from Rs. 350 crore in 2004 to Rs. 800 crore in 2005. After the launch of Indian Government's Project 'Priyadarshini Initiative' for involving more women in the tourism sector in New Delhi, the project is fast gaining in popularity. The three – month course trains women as guides in Mumbai, Pune, Goa, and Ahmadabad, resulting in over 100 new regional tourist guides. These women guides would be certified to work in Maharashtra, Goa, Madhya Pradesh, Chattisgarh, Daman and Diu and Dadra and Nagar, Haveli. The Project aims at increasing women's participation and visibility in the sector, skewed traditionally 80:20 in favour of men. Working as guides women assume the role of ambassadors of the tourism industry and the course imparts the in-depth knowledge necessary for the job.

Women have been playing a vital role not only as tourists but also as service providers in various sectors associated with the tourism industry. Women have availed the numerous opportunities existing in this industry. Many countries, including India, have been making use of this since India has a vast array of protected monuments with 22 world heritage sites, out of which 16 are

monuments. It is employing about 2 crores of people in India. As India's tourism infrastructure develops, it could emerge as one of the biggest tourist attractions "The World is just starting to Re-Discover India".

Tourism Secretary adds that "the Ministry's capacity – building funds will be used to train the women. Female tourists to India will also feel confident travelling by female taxi drivers, accompanied by one female helper". This is significant in the wake of complaints against the capital's unsafe public transport system and increasing crimes against women passengers. One such incident was the rape and murder of an Australian traveller Emily Griggs by two cab drivers playing prepaid taxi, on March 17, 2004.

The programme is that it is a novel attempt to integrate women into the tourism industry as part of the organized sector. Forty-years-old RajniMahajan, a member of the new team, says: "there is nothing that the women of today cannot do. We are flying planes, saving lives and fighting for our country. We are all excited about this new profession and hopefully, more women will join us soon".

Problems of Women Tourists

- Heavy and Multiple taxes, restrictive aviation.
- Complex visa procedures
- Inadequate facilitation services
- Lack of quality and adequate infrastructure – like Transport and the like
- Lack of hygiene and Fear of security
- Lack of emphasis on product quality
- Too many formalities in Airports
- Lack of good quality service and food facilities
- Lack of secured accommodation at the destination
- Non-availability of trained guides
- Exploitation by shoppers and other service providers
- Language problems and other related problems.
- Lack of information about fairs and festivals.

Measures Suggested to Outcome the Problems

The following are the measures suggested to improve the situation to make the Indian Tourism sector one of the best in the world.

- Effective implementation of Government Schemes like 'Guest is God' and Indira Priyadarshini Project and the like.
- Improved awareness of the role of tourism in economic development.
- Providing quality services and 'May I help you desks' at Airports.
- Improving sanitation and hygiene at tourist spots.
- Giving more Publicity through media about tourist places.
- Imparting Training to women guides and women Taxi drivers.
- Providing safe and comfortable tours to the tourist especially to women and those who visit India alone.

Conclusion

Women have proved to be the agents for building capacities of resources in the tourism sector in comparison to men. Hence, the degree of problems faced by women in the tourism sector must require quantification along with the qualitative approach of a study as this. Since there are no data

sources on the actual number of women contributing to the tourism sector in various roles, a proper categorisation is lacking. There is an urgent call to determine the exact number of women working in the tourism sector to make plans and policies to address their work-needs that are unidentified and unaddressed so far. Quantifying and categorising women and their needs based on their roles will provide an illuminating analysis for better use of information on policies and programmes related to the tourism sector.

Women have entered into the tourism industry at different levels. Even the Government of India is also encouraging the involvement of women in more numbers to attract women tourists from foreign countries as well as from other parts of the country. The Government has been taking many measures to provides a safe and comfortable touring to national and international tourists.

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